

Local Government in Argentina

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Argentina is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Argentina: An Introduction

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In Argentina, as in all developing countries, access to local services is a trenchant social issue. The place where you are born determines a large part of your wellbeing, including the probability of not dying at birth, living a longer and decent life, and having access to basic and good quality health, education, and security.

Some figures could give an idea of that link between place of birth and wellbeing. Infant mortality in Formosa is three times larger than in Tierra del Fuego or Buenos Aires.³ Life expectancy in the Province of Chaco is 5 years lower than in Neuquén.⁴ The illiteracy rate in Ramon Lista (13.5 per cent), one of the poorest departments in Formosa, it is 64 times higher than in the Comuna 14, Capital (0.21 per cent).

Improving living conditions of the poorer population plays a fundamental role in achieving sustainable development, and these living conditions depend on the access to basic services, which in most cases depend on subnational units of government. The relevance of this report section to the project is twofold. In the first place, the access to services is significantly influenced by the urban-rural divide. The latter area has extremely low levels of access to most services. It is important to note, however, that not all urban centers enjoy basic service provision across their territories, but coverage in urban areas is considerably larger.

In addition, access to services in Argentina involves the three existing levels of government. In the first place, the federal government plays an obvious role in oversight and regulation. The public services regulative bodies are autonomous agencies within the scope of the executive branch, that check on the quality of provision by private or public companies, which are bestowed with the task of providing and extending public services networks. The provincial (second tier) and local levels play key roles, because the provision of public services has been decentralized to the provinces since the late seventies, and most provinces implemented some form of local decentralization. Therefore, provincial and local governments are in charge of delivering most social services.

Local public service provision in Argentina is an ideal topic to be explored due to its linkages in combination with at least three crucial issues. First, coordination and cooperation in federal countries is relevant because several layers of government are involved in the process of public service provision. It is therefore closely linked with report section 5 on intergovernmental

³ Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos (INDEC), 'Tasa de mortalidad por mil habitantes, según grupo de edad y sexo. Total del país. Años 2012-2016' (INDEC 2016).

⁴ Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos (INDEC), 'Tablas abreviadas de mortalidad 2000-2001. Total País y Provincias' (Documento de Trabajo del Programa Análisis Demográfico No 146, INDEC 2017).

relations of local governments. Secondly, it is also important to take into account that, besides the role of the public sector, local public service provision also depends on the role of civil society. Thirdly, it is also influenced by particularistic interests.

Firstly, provision of local services in Argentina is an ideal opportunity to analyze intergovernmental coordination and cooperation (or conflict) in a federal country. The provision of local services in the country depend on the coordination and collaboration between multiple levels of government. At the national level, despite recent advances in a clearer definition of responsibilities, the institutional framework continues to lack coherence and coordination between federal actors is poor. Being a federal country, the provinces are responsible for delivering most social services, including basic health, primary and secondary education, and public security. The large political, fiscal, and administrative autonomy of the provinces results in a great diversity of institutional arrangements and administrative capacities for the provision of these basic services, and others such as drinking water and sewerage.

Second, the provision of local services is not only a function of coordination or collaboration between units of government. In other words, it does not only depend on the role the public sector pays. Collaboration and even pressures from community organizations and economic interests are also critical factors to consider. In the literature there is a certain consensus that collaboration between the public and private sectors and civil society is fundamental to improve access to services.⁵ On the other hand, a growing urban segregation generates differentiated access to goods and services. For Heller and others,⁶ the place of residence determines the level of basic services to which a person is entitled, generating a 'differentiated citizenship', with unequal access to essential services, such as health, education, and economic opportunities. This research project explicitly focuses on the role of social organizations in allowing the most disadvantaged sectors of society to access resources in possession of the richest sectors.

Thirdly, we argue that the provision of local services also depends on the role of economic interests. When economic elites capture the local state, different sectors of society will be more likely to have differentiated access to services. By state capture we understand a scenario in which politicians are intimately related to dominant economic sectors at the local level. More specifically, where a given local unit has a predominant economic sector, provision of local services is more likely to be either limited or skewed in favor of the dominant economic sector, compared with local units enjoy a diversified economic structure.

Of course, the phenomenon of the concentration of economic power and its impact on the political process occurs in all countries to varying degrees and at different levels of government

⁵ See, for instance: Robert Putnam, Robert Leonardi and Raffaella Nanetti, *Making Democracy Work: Civic Traditions in Modern Italy* (Princeton University Press 1993) 99.

⁶ Patrick Heller, Partha Mukhopadhyay, Subhadra Banda and Shahana Sheikh, 'Exclusion, Informality and Predation in the Cities of Delhi' (Working Paper, New Delhi Centre for Policy Research 2015).

within each country. However, in developing countries the levels of economic power concentration of economic power can lead to excessive overrepresentation of the interests of the powerful, which at its turn affects the level of legitimacy the regime enjoys. Countries with low levels of development (and relatively poorer districts within these countries) have fewer resources for the development of state infrastructure and lower levels of institutionalization that make capture easier, more likely and intense.

In short, public service delivery in Argentina provides an ideal setting to explore state capacities and coordination among levels of government in federal countries, the effect of community organization, and of economic concentration (or diversification) and their effects in the provision of basic services; which at its turn speaks also to democracy and legitimacy.

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This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

